

DECIPHERING THE ROLE OF THE CLASSICAL PROTEIN SECRETION PATHWAY IN THE
TRANSLOCATION OF HSPA1A TO THE CELL SURFACE IN STRESSED AND CANCER CELLS

by

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Deciphering the Role of the Classical Protein Secretion Pathway in the Translocation of HSPA1A to the Cell Surface in Stressed and Cancer Cells

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Abstract

HSPA1A, is a 70-kDa molecular chaperone, which is overproduced in stressed and cancer cells. HSPA1A maintains the cell's dynamic balance and promotes cell survival. Additionally, HSPA1A moves to the cell surface and the extracellular medium of cancer and stressed cells. Cell surface and extracellular HSPA1A promote tumor resistance and alter immune function making this protein an attractive target for new therapeutics. However, how the protein translocates to the cell surface and transports to the extracellular medium remains largely undefined because HSPA1A does not contain known translocation signals. The purpose of this project is to determine the importance of the classical protein secretion pathway by inhibiting the first steps of this pathway. To this end, cells were treated with two compounds that both disrupt the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) to Golgi protein transfer using different mechanisms, and after heat-shock cell surface HSPA1A was quantified using confocal microscopy. Preliminary results using both compounds suggest that HSPA1A's cell surface translocation is independent of the ER-Golgi pathway. These results, which are currently being finalized and controlled, provide important first clues as to the mechanism of HSPA1A's translocation in stressed and cancer cells.

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Introduction

Cancer is a life-threatening condition affecting the lives of millions every year all over the world. To provide knowledge and contribute to its cure, I will characterize how a molecule (a protein) finds itself in the wrong place at the wrong time, an ability that directly affects the cancer patient's prognosis and disease state. In the following paragraphs, I will provide basic information on cancer and the protein I will be studying, why it is important to study this protein, and what my project concerns.

The purpose of this literature review is to familiarize the reader with basic concepts and ideas of my project and my research questions. In the later chapters, I will be describing the research questions and the objectives of my project. Lastly, I will provide some basic methodological concepts, and a conclusion statement.

Background on Cancer

Cancer is one ailment that places stress on cells and cellular processes. Cancer cells reproduce uninhibited and ultimately lead to the formation of a tumor. These cells show major genomic, transcriptional, and metabolic alterations. One research study found that “at the cellular level, the development of cancer is viewed as a multistep process involving mutation and selection for cells with progressively increasing capacity for proliferation, survival, invasion, and metastasis” (Cooper et. al., 2000). Some additional characteristics of cancer cells are that they contain larger

than the average size for a nucleus and have an unusual number of chromosomes that are not bound within the nucleus.

A tumor is any build-up of cells due to unregulated cell growth. There are two categories of tumors, benign and malignant. A benign tumor is one whose cells remain tethered in their location, not spreading to other areas of the body. A malignant tumor, however, is one that invades the normal tissues surrounding it or even uses the circulatory system to spread throughout the body (Cooper et. al., 2000).

Proteins and HSP70 (HSPA1A)

Protein placement within tumor cells often play critical roles in whether a tumor remains benign or turns malignant. Proteins are translated from amino acids that are transcribed when RNA polymerase copies DNA strands into an RNA sequence. Protein functions are often defined by where they are located within a cell. HSP70s is part of the 70-kDa family of heat shock proteins known to be “molecular chaperones.”

Molecular chaperones are essentially proteins that keep a cell alive by correcting misfolded polypeptides (chains of amino acids) so that they may reassume the roles that they were meant to carry out within the cell (Radons 2016). The chaperones within the HSP70 family are responsible for maintaining homeostasis and stable cell conditions by unfolding and refolding proteins to help the cell withstand both stressful and pathologically harmful conditions.

Function of HSPA1A

HSP70s are stress-inducible, which means that their production is increased (the proteins are expressed at a higher concentration) when cells experience stress due to intracellular or extracellular factors. The HSP70 that can primarily be correlated with disease in humans is HSP70-1, more commonly known as HSPA1A.

While proteins possess numerous beneficiary functions within a cell, research has found that HSPA1A has three prerogatives within cells and those are:

1. To maintain homeostasis in proteins by reverting them to their original states following the effects of protein unfolding or denaturation due to heat and stress.
2. To carry out its role as a “molecular chaperone” and facilitate protein transport across the membranes of membrane-bound organelles such as the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and the mitochondria.
3. To regulate other proteins and ultimately cell survival by:
 - a. Binding to proteins that would otherwise become toxic to the cell.
 - b. Interfering with cellular signaling pathways that are responsible for producing TNF (tumor necrosis factor) that are produced by macrophages and influence cell apoptosis to fight off cancers and other infections (Wang et. al., 2008).

Ultimately, the goal of HSPA1A is to, at almost all costs, find a way to keep the cells alive. While in most cases such a protein would prove advantageous to cells, when it comes to cancerous and tumor cells, such a tendency would be detrimental as it would keep the diseased cell alive and even facilitate its replication and transport.

Figure 1. This image depicts the two starkly contrasting effects of HSPA1A on a cancerous cell versus a tumor cell (PMID:23845032).

HSPA1A Localization at the Plasma Membrane (PM) and the Extracellular Medium (EM)

The plasma (or cell) membrane is the barrier between the inside and the outside (extracellular medium) environments of the cell. In stressed and tumor cells, HSPA1A is overproduced in the cytoplasm (inside) to aid cell survival. Additionally, HSPA1A also translocates and embeds at the PM of several types of cancer cells (Bilog, et. al., 2019).

The presence of HSPA1A at the PM renders tumor cells resistant to cytotoxic and external cancer therapeutic treatments such as radiation (Guzhova, et. al., 2013). Additionally, HSPA1A presence at the PM of tumor cells has been found to make those specific cells more likely to implement invasive tendencies against surrounding cell tissues as well as an increased propensity for developing metastasis, and the tumor becoming malignant rather than benign.

In contrast, the presence of HSPA1A on the surface of the tumor cell could serve as a distinguishing factor/beacon that allows for the recognition of the cell as potentially pathogenic and triggers an immune or apoptotic response (Guzhova, et. al., 2013). How these two contradictory ideas have been attributed to this protein remains unknown although it has been proposed that the deciding factor may be the orientation of the protein at the surface and whether it carries any antigens.

To make matters more fascinating, although more complex, HSPA1A had also been found in the EM of cancer cells. Depending on the fashion of export, HSPA1A at the EM has been shown to result in activating (immunostimulant) or inhibiting (immunosuppressant) the immune responses against these cancers. Different reports have designated distinct mechanisms as HSPA1A has been found both in extracellular vesicles and as free protein in the EM. While it can be concluded that an overexpression of HSPA1A at the PM, can result in aggressive and metastatic cancers (Murphy 2013), there remains a serious amount of ambiguity regarding which specific pathway and mechanisms allow for this translocation to occur. There have been parallels drawn between the transport of HSPA1A and three possible mechanisms: exosomes (extracellular vesicles that have been excreted from the cell), secretory lysozymes (degrades and stores secreted cell proteins), and direct membrane binding. Although the aforementioned reports delineated pathways responsible for HSPA1A's export some are contradictory and do not clarify the relationship between PM and EM localized HSPA1A.

One could envision that if we decrease the immunosuppressant forms of HSPA1A and increase the immunostimulant forms of the protein we will render tumors sensitive to current therapies and increase the natural immunity (our body’s ability to fight disease) against the tumor itself. My project aims, as part of the work conducted in our lab, to provide knowledge on these specific pathways and routes that HSPA1A uses to reach the PM and EM. Identifying the specific pathways involved in these processes we will be able to generate compounds that alter them to render cancers sensitive to therapy and induce the immune system to destroy them.

Figure 2. This image depicts the possible cellular transport pathways of HSPA1A beginning at the nucleus and ending at the exterior, or extracellular space of the cell. (<https://doi.org/10.1002/cplu.202100304>).

HSPA1A and Lipids

Multiple studies found that the HspA1A interacts with negatively charged lipids, suggesting interactions with the lipid head, and neutral lipids suggesting interactions with the acyl chains, and these interactions mediate HspA1A’s PM-localization and secretion (Calderwood, Mambula, Gray,

& Theriault, 2007; Lancaster & Febbraio, 2005; Mambula et al., 2007; Arispe, Doh, & De Maio, 2002; Arispe et al., 2004; Armijo et al., 2014; Gehrmann et al., 2008; Mamelak & Lingwood, 2001; McCallister, Kdeiss, & Nikolaidis, 2015a, 2015b; McCallister, Kdeiss, Oliverio, & Nikolaidis, 2016; McCallister, Siracusa, Shirazi, Chalkia, & Nikolaidis, 2015; Schilling et al., 2009; Vega et al., 2008).

These lipids include globotriaosylceramide (GB3), a major constituent of lipid rafts (Gehrmann et al., 2008) and phosphatidylserine (PS), a major constituent of the plasma membrane (Arispe et al., 2004; Armijo et al., 2014; Lamprecht et al., 2018; McCallister, Kdeiss, et al., 2015a, 2015b; McCallister, Siracusa, et al., 2015; Schilling et al., 2009; Bilog et al., 2019). In addition to these lipids, results from the Nikolaidis Lab revealed that binding of HspA1A to PI(3)P (present in early endosomes) and PI(4)P (present in Golgi, late endosomes, and the PM) is critical for the chaperone to attach itself onto the PM arguing in favor of a vesicular trafficking mechanism.

Cancer and HSPA1A

All cancer cells overexpress HspA1A, a molecular chaperone, member of the heat shock protein family (Horvath et al., 2008). Overexpression of HspA1A has major clinical significance because the protein promotes cell survival and inhibits cell death resulting in tumor aggression and metastasis. In addition to its functions inside the cell, HspA1A is also present on the tumor-cell surface, where it renders cells insensitive to current therapies (Schilling et al., 2009).

Understanding the cellular functions of HspA1A when present at the cell surface is essential to generate new treatments, repurpose current anti-cancer compounds, and improve patient prognosis. To achieve these goals, it is imperative to determine the mechanism and pathways that result in HspA1A's surface presentation, which remain largely undefined. Below, I provide basic information on the cellular functions of this protein and its roles in stressed and tumor cells.

Therefore, if there is a way to understand how HSPA1A travels and interacts with other aspects of the cells, i.e., the lipids, exosomes, and secretory vesicles, it could be possible to manipulate these interactions to be able to force apoptosis in cancerous cells that may otherwise keep replicating and spreading throughout the body.

Aims and Objectives

The function of HSPA1A is related to its placement within a cell and to be able to manipulate this function, it is essential to understand the pathways and factors that influence its localization. By investigating the ambiguity surrounding the pathway taken by HSPA1A that transports it to different parts of the cell, as well as how the placement of this heat shock protein affects tumor cells in the development of cancerous tumors.

The main objective of this research is to determine whether certain compounds known to affect protein secretion and vesicular translocation alter HSPA1A's plasma membrane location. To do so, certain drugs will be tested against human cancer cell lines. These drugs are designed to inhibit pathways (for membrane localization and exocytosis/endocytosis).

Methodology

For my experiments I will use specific human cell lines (HEK293 and HeLa) and a heat-shock model to simulate the cancer condition. This heat-shock model consists of incubation of cells at 42°C for 1 hour followed by cell recovery at their normal growth temperature (37°C). It is well established that HSPA1A translocates to the PM of human cells after heat-shock (Bilog et. al., 2019). Specifically, immediately after heat shock the PM localized HSPA1A increases and reaches a maximum at 8 hours of recovery. My goal is to use specific compounds (drugs) and identify which ones alter this pattern. I care for drugs that both increase and decrease this pattern.

To visualize and quantify the amount of HSPA1A at the PM, I will use a well-established assay in our laboratory, that quantifies proteins using confocal microscopy. For confocal imaging experiments, I will pass the cells on poly-lysine D coated coverslips. After heat shock, the coverslips will be mounted on slides using DAPI Fluoromount-G® (SouthernBiotech) and will be visualized by using Olympus FV3000 confocal microscope equipped with a 63× 1.4 oil objective. After imaging is completed, I will determine HspA1A's relocalization based on the CTCF (corrected total cell fluorescence) ratio between the total GFP-HspA1A fluorescence (green) and the rest of the cell [CTCF = integrated density – (area of selected cell × mean fluorescence of background readings)].

Figure 3. This image provides a depiction of the processes utilized when completing the procedure outlined above to test the effects of the pharmaceutical drugs, BFA and Exo1, on the transport of HSPA1A from the endoplasmic reticulum to the Golgi.

The drugs used aim to disrupt the classical secretion and PM localization pathways and include tetanus toxin (this zinc protease cleaves SNARE proteins and inhibits the fusion of vesicles to the PM); DMA 5-(N,N-Dimethyl)amiloride hydrochloride (selectively inhibits Na/H exchangers in cellular membranes and inhibits exosomes); DIDS 4,4'-Diisothiocyanatostilbene-2,2'-disulfonic acid disodium salt hydrate (is a specific inhibitor of cellular anion permeability and inhibits calcium transport in vesicles); Tunicamycin (blocks all N-glycosylation of proteins); Brefeldin A (inhibits protein transport from the endoplasmic reticulum to the Golgi complex); Monensin sodium salt (Na⁺ ionophore; blocks glycoprotein secretion); Bafilomycin A1 (an inhibitor of endosomal acidification); U73122 (a pharmacological inhibitor of phospholipase C activity); methyl-beta-cyclodextrin and filipin (deplete cholesterol from the PM).

The aforementioned drugs are all hypothesized to have an effect on the cellular location of the HSPA1A protein. For the purposes of this research, I will be looking specifically at the effects of BFA and Exo1 when it comes to inhibiting protein vesicular trafficking from the endoplasmic reticulum to the Golgi.

Brefeldin A (BFA)

Brefeldin A (BFA) is a fungal metabolite that inhibits various cellular processes by blocking the transport of proteins across certain pathways. More specifically, BFA can block two endomembrane systems – the ER to Golgi system and the post-Golgi (trans-Golgi network) system that transports proteins to the cellular surface (Miller et. al., 1992). This paper will look at the former, rather than the latter and study whether blocking the ER-Golgi pathway with BFA affects the presence of HSPA1A at the plasma membrane, although the mechanisms and means by which this occurs overlap in both instances. BFA inhibits the Golgi secretion by causing morphological and functional changes in the Golgi tubulates and sending all the contents back to the endoplasmic

reticulum. The shift in tubulates is triggered by an ADP ribosylation event that triggers the tube conformation results in a membrane curvature that alters the shape and functionality of the cell. On a microscopic scale, the restriction of items meant to be excised from the cell can often result in protein aggregation within the ER. By extension, increased ER stress levels can be grounds for proteins to initiate apoptotic processes within cells. A key factor to note when it comes to BFA is that it only blocks the forward mechanism of exocytosis, but not the reverse (endocytosis) mechanism. One source indicates that the primary target of BFA in cells is ADP-ribosylation factor-1 (ARF1). Treatment with BFA significantly and rapidly decreases the activated ARF1 levels on the membrane and consequently activating more proteins and pathways that lead to the collapse of the Golgi (Feng et. al, 2003).

Figure 4. Depicted above is a diagram of the cellular pathways that are inhibited by BFA. It is important to take note that only the exocytotic pathways are blocked, but not the endocytic pathways (InvivoGen. June 6, 2020. Brefeldin A. InvivoGen. <https://www.invivoqen.com/bfa#citations>).

2-(4-Fluorobenzoylamino)-Benzoic Acid Methyl Ester (Exo1)

2-(4-Fluorobenzoylamino)-Benzoic Acid Methyl Ester, also known as Exo1, has a similar function to that of BFA. While the result is similar, the mechanisms for how these two drugs inhibit protein trafficking from the endoplasmic reticulum to the Golgi vary. The one glaring difference between Exo1 and BFA is that unlike BFA, Exo1 does not induce ADP-ribosylation and therefore, allows for the release of the ADP-ribosylation factor from the membrane and prevents its interference in the exchange of the guanine nucleotide. It is stated within the Feng paper that “either Exo1 binds to a subset of the protein targets of BFA or the target of Exo1 is different from that of BFA” (Feng, 2019). It is hypothesized that the target for Exo1 is further downstream than the ARF1 step in which GTP is loaded.

Since Exo1 has no apparent impact on the endosomes, it can be a “a valuable reagent to study the consequences of perturbations of the ER and Golgi traffic for the movement of ligands from the plasma membrane to the ER” (Feng et. al., 2003).

Figure 5. This image shows the overall effects of the two drugs on the Golgi as time passes, over the span of ten minutes. (A). Tubular distribution highlighted within the Golgi using the GalT-GFP. The technique used to obtain the image was fluorescence microscopy in BSC1 cells. (B). Represents the strength of the Golgi signals as Exo1 and BFA are added. (C). Represents the initial and post treatment conditions of endosomes within the Golgi following treatment with BFA and Exo1. (DOI: [10.1073/pnas.0631766100](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0631766100)).

As is seen within the figure, there is a significant difference in the Golgi bodies within each cell with the use of Exo1 and BFA. The BFA caused an enlargement in the overall size of the Golgi, which indicates that it affects the endosomes and inner tubulates. The Exo1 on the other hand, resulted in a collapse of the Golgi, but not the endosomes (as seen in Part C of Figure 5).

Results

The CTCF (corrected total cell fluorescence) was found to be in accordance with the expected results in terms of the boxplot patterns. In figure 7, plot that compared the DMSO with the effects of BFA, it was found that the results for the control and the drug were near identical in their CTCF (PM/cytosol) ratios. This would indicate that contrary to previous speculations, that while BFA is known to prevent ER to Golgi transport, in the specific case of looking to disrupt HSPA1A transport, there was no effect. Since the objective was to test drugs meant to inhibit certain cellular pathways within a cell, the fact that the readings for BFA were near identical to DMSO means that the proposed pathway that was inhibited by the BFA is not one that is commonly used by HSPA1A since there was no significant change in the presence of HSPA1A at the membrane after the cell was treated with BFA under stressful conditions and at three different conditions as outlined previously (0, 8, and 37).

The Exo1, in comparison to the results obtained with BFA, was slightly different. Exo1 showed slight differences in the CTCF ratio at the plasma membrane, which indicates that a potential impact of Exo1 on HSPA1A, however, the shift was not significant to yield any conclusive results. Therefore, there is a chance that the Exo1 inhibited pathway of protein trafficking is employed by HSPA1A, although more experimentation would be required to confirm or deny such claims.

Figure 6. The images indicated were collected using confocal microscopy. Prior to imaging, the cells were stained with GFP (green-fluorescence protein), PM (plasma membrane) stain, and DAPI (stains for the nucleus).

Figure 7. This figure depicts the presence of HSPA1A at the plasma membrane of cells when treated with the control, DMSO, and BFA. DMSO was used as a vesicle control (N=20). Quantification of the corrected total cell fluorescence (CTCF) is a ratio of the presence of the green fluorescence protein (GFP) at the plasma membrane as opposed to the rest of the cell. There are three conditions at which each of the drugs were tested -37 represents a control at room temperature (37°C), 0 represents a zero-hour recovery time at 37°C, and 8 represents an eight-hour recovery time at 37°C.

Figure 8. Figure 6. This is a depiction of the presence of HSPA1A at the plasma membrane of cells when treated with the control, DMSO, and Exo1. DMSO was used as a vesicle control (N=20). Quantification of the corrected total cell fluorescence (CTCF) is a ratio of the green fluorescence protein (GFP) at the plasma membrane as opposed to the rest of the cell. There are three conditions at which each of the drugs were tested –37 represents a control at room temperature (37°C), 0 represents a zero-hour recovery time at 37°C, and 8 represents an eight-hour recovery time at 37°C.

Discussion

HSPA1A is a heat shock response protein that is upregulated and more frequently produced in cancerous or stressed cellular conditions. Membrane bound HSPA1A is evident in more than eighty percent of tested tumors and determining the mechanism that drives HSPA1A to the membrane will allow manipulation of this pathway to impact tumor survival.

While there are still countless pathways and drug treatments that can be utilized to help determine HSPA1A’s cellular pathway, specific to the results obtained by the testing conducted with BFA and Exo1, it can be concluded that HSPA1A’s cell surface translocation is independent of

the ER-Golgi pathway. HSPA1A's cell surface translocation is unaffected from BFA and minimally affected from Exo1.

Cytokines and growth factors are the primary “fuel” on which cancer cells survive. These proteins are transported to the cellular surface and most other parts of the cell by passing through the Golgi. Essentially, what Exo1 and BFA are doing when it comes to cancer cells, is that they are preventing the transport of these proteins and depriving the cells of the growth factors needed to facilitate metastasis (Bajaj et. al., 2022). The idea behind the use of BFA and Exo1 for my specific experiment is that if a known anti-proliferative drug in cancer cells can cause a lower count of HSPA1A (a known apoptotic inhibitor) to be present at the plasma membrane, then there is a chance that one of the ER-Golgi pathways that BFA and Exo1 inhibits is the same pathway through which HSPA1A travels through the cell. Knowing the pathway of the HSPA1A through the cell would help to narrow down the search to find a therapeutic drug that could effectively inhibit the specific route that HSPA1A takes to get from the cytosol to the plasma membrane of a cell. It would be a preventative measure because once HSPA1A reaches the plasma membrane, it renders the cell resistant to cytotoxic chemotherapy treatments (anti-apoptotic).

Treatment with BFA is typically administered with the aim of making cancerous cells more susceptible to cytotoxic chemotherapy drugs and triggering apoptosis. BFA is a well-known pharmaceutical drug that has anti-proliferative effects on cancer cells in general. However, when studied in conjunction with HSPA1A's movement throughout a cancer cell, the results revealed that there was no significant shift in the concentration of HSPA1A at the plasma membrane. The results of the experiment hint at the fact that the level of cell susceptibility is likely to vary over the different types of cancers and the subsequent cellular and experimental conditions. Aside from a slight deviation between the control and the Exo1, a similar result was obtained, since the HSPA1A concentration measured at the membrane was not significant enough to be conclusive.

Conclusion

A fundamental issue in cancer research is the fact that almost each cancer type is unique and different individual patients respond very differently in the same type of therapy. In contrast, HSPA1A's mechanism of action inside the cell, at the cell surface, and the extracellular medium is very well conserved and seems to be universal between all cancer types that have been studied to date. Therefore, HSPA1A offers the exclusive opportunity to target simultaneously many tumors and target the immune system against them.

By determining the different pathways that this protein uses to reach these unconventional parts of the body we will be able to alter the balance to HSPA1A's forms that activate the immune system and cause cell death and have a much better chance of helping the patients. To achieve these ambitious objectives, we need to understand the basic mechanisms that this protein is using to reach the cell surface and the extracellular medium.

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